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Baz2b marks the luminal A subtype.

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Epigenetic factors regulate stage- and cell type-specific gene expression. The functional importance of imprinting system-associated epigenetic machinery in Xist control of transformation and subtype selection in human cancer is not completely understood. We describe here subtype-specific expression of a bromodomain-containing adapter molecule, Baz2a, in the luminal A tumor subtype in humans with breast cancer. The Xist RNP recently identified as a component of autosomal gene regulation in normal and transformed cells is thus a central determinant of lineage specification in solid tumors of the breast through Baz1/Baz2-based RNP complex composition alteration.